

VARIASION TENGSIZLIKLAR ASOSIDA DINAMIK SISTEMALARNING KIRISH TA'SIRLARINI TIKLASH ALGORITMLARI

Qodirov Dilmurod To'xtasinovich

NamMTI Phd.dots

Sharibboyev Shoxjaxon Sharibboy o'g'li

NamMTI desertant

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8062738>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 15-June 2023 yil

Ma'qullandi: 18-June 2023 yil

Nashr qilindi: 21-June 2023 yil

KEY WORDS

Yuqorida va to'plam shartini qanoatlantiradi, ushbu to'plamlar ayrim ma'noda "teng" yaqinlikka mos keladi, deb faraz qilindi

ABSTRACT

Ushbu maqolada G'alayonlar sohasini hisob-kitob qilishda mos kelmaslik prinsipidan muntazamlashtirish parametrini tanlash va operatorli muntazamlashtirish uslubining o'xshashligi haqidagi masalani ko'rib chiqamiz,

Ushbu maqolada G'alayonlar sohasini hisob-kitob qilishda mos kelmaslik prinsipidan muntazamlashtirish parametrini tanlash va operatorli muntazamlashtirish uslubining o'xshashligi haqidagi masalani ko'rib chiqamiz, matrisaga nisbatan rekurrent tenglamalar sistemasini ko'rib chiqamiz:

$$(\delta^2 I_m + \tilde{F}^T \tilde{F} - \lambda_* D)\theta = \tilde{F}^T \tilde{y}^*, \quad \delta > 0. \quad (1.1)$$

(2.2) dagi F operatorlar barcha $\delta \geq 0$ da quyidagi xususiyatga ega bo'ladi deb faraz qilamiz:

$$\|F\theta - y_\delta^*\| \leq c_1 (\|\theta - \theta^0\| + 1), \quad \forall \theta \in T, \quad (1.2)$$

bu yerda: $c_1 > 0$ -ayrim o'zgarmaslar, θ^0 - H dan belgilangan nuqta.

θ ning yechimini hisoblash uchun muntazamlashtirishning operator uslubidan foydalanamiz:

$$(F\theta + \alpha(\theta - \theta^0) - y_\delta^*, z - \theta) \geq 0, \quad \forall z \in K_\sigma, \theta \in K_\sigma, \quad (1.3)$$

bu yerda: $\alpha > 0$.

θ_γ - (1.3) ning yagona yechimi bo'lsin; bu yerda $\gamma = (\delta, \sigma, \alpha)$. Demak, shunday $F\theta_\gamma$ element topilsinki, quyidagi munosabat haqiqiy bo'lsin

$$(F\theta_\gamma + \alpha(\theta_\gamma - \theta^0) - y_\delta^*, z - \theta_\gamma) \geq 0, \quad \forall z \in K_\sigma. \quad (1.4)$$

U holda, (1.2) va (1.4) asosida quyidagicha yozish mumkin

$$\alpha(\theta_\gamma - \theta^0, \theta_\gamma - \nu_\gamma) \leq (F\theta - y_\delta^*, u_\gamma - \theta_\gamma) + (F\theta_\gamma - y_\delta^*, \nu_\gamma - \theta) + \delta \|\theta - \theta_\gamma\|, \quad (1.5)$$

bu yerda $\theta \in N$ va barcha $z \in K$, $u_\gamma \in K$, $v_\gamma \in K_\sigma$ da $(F\theta - y^*, z - \theta) \geq 0$ tengsizlik bajariladi, shu bilan birga $\|\theta_\gamma - u_\gamma\| \leq \sigma$, $\|\theta - v_\gamma\| \leq \sigma$.

Keyin, (1.2) va (1.5) dan kelib chiqib quyidagiga ega bo'lamiz:

$$\|\theta_\gamma - \theta^0\| \leq \delta/\alpha + c_1\sigma/\alpha + 2\|\theta - \theta^0\| + 2 + \sigma.$$

Agar ko'rib chiqilayotgan shartda $\alpha \rightarrow 0$ da δ/α , $\sigma/\alpha \rightarrow 0$ bo'lsa, u holda $\{\theta_\gamma\}$ ketma-ketlik $\alpha \rightarrow 0$ da quyidagi tenglik

$$\|\theta^* - \theta^0\| = \min_{\theta \in N} \|\theta - \theta^0\|.$$

bilan aniqlanuvchi $\theta^* \in N$ element H ga kuchli yaqinlashishiniko'rsatish mumkin.

Yuqorida K va K_σ to'plam $r(K, K_\sigma) \leq \sigma$ shartini qanoatlantiradi, ushbu to'plamlar ayrim ma'noda "teng" yaqinlikka mos keladi, deb faraz qilindi. Biroq masalaning keng doirasi uchun ushbu shart bajarilmaydi. Masalan, agar, $K \subset R_2$ da - cheklangan to'plam va cheklov $y = ax + b$ chiziqli funksiya bilan berilsa, u holda a koeffitsiyentidagi har qanday yetarli kichik xatoda $r(K, K_\sigma) = \infty$ bo'ladi. Shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, K cheklangan to'plamda $r(K, K_\sigma) \leq \sigma$ sharti tabiiy hisoblanadi.

K to'plam chegaralanmagan deb hisoblansin, R ni juda katta deb olsak, K_σ^R va $N \cap K^R = M^R$ bo'sh bo'lmasligi mumkin. $r(K^R, K_\sigma^R) \leq \sigma$ deb faraz qilamiz. Qo'yilgan masalani K^R (R belgilangan) da muhokama qilib, $\bar{\theta}^* \in N_R$ elementiga muntazamlashtirilgan yechimni olamiz, bu yerda N_R - quyidagi

$$(F\theta - y^*, z - \theta) \geq 0 \quad \forall z \in K^R, \theta \in K^R, \quad (1.6)$$

tengsizlik yechimining to'plami, shu bilan birga

$$\|\bar{\theta}^* - \theta^0\| = \min_{\theta \in N_R} \|\theta - \theta^0\|.$$

N_R va M^R to'plami qavariq [77, 78], u holda $\theta \in N_R \setminus M^R$ va $\theta \in \partial K^R$ mavjud bo'lsa, $\bar{\theta} \in N_R \setminus M^R$, $\bar{\theta} \in \text{int } K^R$ ham topiladi. Shubhasiz, $N_R = M^R$. Demak, (1) ni o'rniga (1.6) ifodadan foydalanish mumkin va unga muntazamlashtirishni qo'llab, $\theta^* \in N$ topish kerak.

θ_α - quyidagi tengsizlikning yagona yechimi deb faraz qilamiz,

$$(F\theta_\alpha + \alpha(\theta - \theta^0) - y^*, z - \theta) \geq 0, \quad \forall z \in K. \quad (1.7)$$

Demak

$$(F\theta_\alpha + \alpha(\theta_\alpha - \theta^0) - y^*, z - \theta_\alpha) \geq 0, \quad \forall z \in K.$$

$z = \theta^0$ bo'lganda oxirgi tengsizlikdan

$$(F\theta_\alpha - y^*, \theta_\alpha - \theta^0) + \alpha\|\theta_\alpha - \theta^0\|^2 \leq 0 \text{ olish mumkin, ya'ni } (F\theta_\alpha - y^*, \theta_\alpha - \theta^0) \leq 0,$$

bu holda $\theta_{t+1}^\delta = \theta_t^\delta + \frac{\gamma_k^\delta(t)\theta_t^\delta(k)}{\delta^2/\lambda_* - p_{kk}^\delta(t)}$ dan $\{\theta_\mu\} \subset \{\theta_\alpha\}$, $\theta_\mu \rightarrow \bar{\theta}$ ketma-ketligining mavjudligi kelib

chiqadigan quyidagi ifodaga ega bo'lamiz:

$$\|\theta_\alpha - \theta^0\| \leq R, \quad (1.8)$$

Ko'rib chiqilgan shartlarda (1.7) ifoda $(F\theta + \alpha(z - \theta^0) - y^*, z - \theta_\alpha) \geq 0$ tengsizlikka ekvivalentdir. Oxirgi nisbatga $\alpha = \mu$ ni qo'yib va $\mu \rightarrow 0$ ga o'tib, $(F\theta - y^*, z - \bar{\theta}) \geq 0$ ni, ya'ni $\bar{\theta}$ - yechimni olamiz. Bundan tashqari, (1.8) dan quyidagi kelib chiqadi: $\|\bar{\theta} - \theta^0\| \leq R$.

Ko'pincha K va K_σ to'plamlarning yaqinligi quyidagi ifoda asosida aniqlanadi [3, 4]:

$$S(R, K, K_\sigma) = \sup_{v \in K^R} \inf_{u \in K_\sigma} \|u - v\|, \quad \forall R \geq 0.$$

Shu bilan birga, agar K^R bo'sh bo'lsa, u holda hech bo'lmaganda K_σ^R yoki K^R to'plamlaridan biri bo'sh bo'lmasa, $S(R, K, K_\sigma) = 0$ hisoblanadi, u holda $\tau(R, K, K_\sigma) = \max\{S(R, K, K_\sigma), S(R, K_\sigma, K)\}$ ekanligi ko'rib chiqiladi.

$$\tau(R, K, K_\sigma) \leq a(R)\sigma, \quad \text{bu yerda } R \rightarrow \infty$$

$$(F\theta + \alpha E^a(\theta - \theta^0) - y_\delta^*, z - \theta) \geq 0, \quad \forall z \in K_\sigma, \theta \in K_\sigma, \quad (1.9)$$

bo'lganda $a(R) (R \geq 0)$, $a(R) \rightarrow \infty$ bo'lishini ta'kid qilamiz. Bu yerda $\theta \neq 0$ va $E^a(0) = 0$ bo'lganda $E^a : H \rightarrow H$, $E^a(\theta) = a(\|\theta\|)\theta/\|\theta\|$ bo'ladi.

Avvalgidek (1.9) ning yechimini θ_γ orqali belgilaymiz.

(1.5) ga o'xshash, quyidagicha yozish mumkin:

$$a(\|\theta_\gamma - \theta^0\|) \left[\|\theta_\gamma - \theta^0\| - c_2 - c_1(\|\theta - \theta^0\| + 1) \frac{\sigma}{\alpha} \right] - \quad (1.10)$$

$$- \|\theta_\gamma - \theta^0\| \left[\frac{\delta}{\alpha} + c_1 a(\|\theta - \theta^0\|) \frac{\sigma}{\alpha} \right] - \frac{\delta}{\alpha} \|\theta - \theta^0\| + c_1 a(\|\theta - \theta^0\|) \frac{\sigma}{\alpha} \leq 0,$$

bu yerda: $c_2 = \|\theta - \theta^0\| + a(\|\theta - \theta^0\|)\sigma$.

$\alpha \rightarrow 0$ da δ/α , $\sigma/\alpha \rightarrow 0$ bo'lsin, u holda (2.17) ifodadan ko'rinib turibdiki, $\|\theta_\gamma\| \leq C$ va γ ga bog'liq bo'lmagano'zgarimas C mavjud.

Shunday qilib, agar $\alpha \rightarrow 0$ da δ/α , $\sigma/\alpha \rightarrow 0$ bo'lsa, u holda $\{\theta_\gamma\}$ ketma-ketlik $\theta^* \in N$ elementga kuchli yaqinlashadi.

Xulosa

Olingan ifodalar muntazamlashtirishning operator uslubidan foydalanib variasion tengsizliklar asosida izlanayotgan yechimlar o'xshashligini ta'minlashga imkon beradi.

Foydalanilgan adaboyotlar ro'yxati:

1. Bakushinskiy A.B., Goncharskiy A.V. Iterativniy metodi risheniya nekorriktniy zadach
2. Musina R., Nazarov A.I., Variational inequalities for the spectral fractional Laplacian // Zh.
3. Klimov V.S., Demyankov N.A. Otnositelnoye vrasheniye i variatsionnyye neravenstva // Izv. vuzov.
4. Yarlykov M.S. Primeneniye markovskiy teorii nelineynoy filtratsii v radiotexnike. - M.: Radio, 1980